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MEDIA & COMMUNICATION RESEARCH & PRACTICE

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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CONFERENCE OVERVIEW

The **Media and Communication Research and Practice 2025** International Conference was held on **19–20 June 2025** in Bucharest, Romania, in a **hybrid format** combining in-person and online participation. Organised by the **Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences, University of Bucharest**, the conference provided a forum for scholarly exchange on key transformations affecting media, communication, and public life in a digitally mediated environment.

The conference brought together **45 papers**, authored by **78 researchers**, representing **25 academic and research institutions** from **15 countries** across Europe, Africa, and the Mediterranean region. Contributions reflected a broad range of disciplinary perspectives and methodological approaches, highlighting the diversity and international scope of contemporary media and communication research.

The programme addressed three main thematic areas: **political communication in the context of digital transformation, changes in media systems and journalistic practice**, and **marketing and strategic communication in the digital age**. Across these themes, participants examined issues such as elections and digital populism, trust and disinformation, artificial intelligence and algorithmic governance, journalism education and professional risks, platformised communication, and evolving marketing and advertising practices.

The abstracts collected in this volume document the intellectual contributions presented at the conference and offer insight into current debates shaping media and communication scholarship. Together, they reflect ongoing efforts to critically assess the role of communication in democratic processes, institutional change, and cultural production in an increasingly data-driven and platform-dependent public sphere.

Selected contributions from the conference were further developed and published in the **Romanian Journal of Journalism and Communication (RJJC)**. The first two issues released following the conference include **10 peer-reviewed articles** originating from conference presentations, reflecting both the thematic diversity and scholarly quality of the event. These issues are available online at:

<https://journals.unibuc.ro/index.php/rjic/issue/archive>

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From trust to skepticism: Has influencer marketing reached its breaking point? - Stela AGO (Universidade Católica Portuguesa, Portugal), Alexandre DUARTE (ICNOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal)

Purpose

Influencer marketing has evolved into an effective hybrid between traditional endorsements and authentic digital communication (Campbell & Farrell, 2020). Initially appreciated for its ability to convey authenticity and build trust, it is now facing a growing skepticism due to excessive commercialization, market saturation, and an increasing critical consciousness among consumers (Ki et al., 2022; Pradhan et al., 2022). While influencers still offer a more organic alternative to traditional advertising, recent studies (Ki et al., 2022) highlight how their effectiveness is compromised by perceived inauthenticity, excessive brand control, and declining trust.

Authenticity, transparency, and credibility represent the key pillars of influencer marketing effectiveness, and trust can be fostered through genuine content, transparent disclosures, and a strong coherence between influencers' values and those of the target audiences (Fileri et al., 2022; Weismueller et al., 2020). However, transparency can also generate paradoxical effects, if on the one hand it increases the perceived authenticity, which is essential to build trust, on the other hand it can reduce engagement when content is perceived as overly promotional (Martínez-López et al., 2020). Furthermore, the influencer category plays a crucial role; micro-influencers tend to maintain stronger relationships with their audiences thanks to a higher perceived accessibility and authenticity, while macro- and mega-influencers risk losing credibility due to a higher exposure and to over-commercialization of content (Pradhan et al., 2022; Conde & Casais, 2023).

Design/methodology/approach

Two case studies analysis. 1) the *Pandoro Gate* scandal involving Italy's top influencer, Chiara Ferragni, who, in 2023, was fined over €1 million by the Italian antitrust authority for misleading consumers into believing that the purchase of a branded Christmas cake would fund a children's hospital, although the donation had been made months earlier and was unrelated to the sales (Vock, 2023). This case is particularly significant because it shows how even one of the most well-known worldwide influencers can lose credibility, creating a wider public distrust toward influencer marketing.

2) The second case is related to Matilda Djerf, who was recently accused by former employees of creating a toxic work environment, contrasting sharply with her carefully curated image on social media (Acheson, 2024). This case also highlights the gap between influencers' public

personas and their real behavior, which can have a strong impact on perceptions of authenticity and trust

(Potential) Findings

To remain relevant, influencer marketing needs to adapt to this landscape, prioritizing authentic collaborations, value-based alignments, and strategic partnerships. Brands should give influencers creative freedom and focus on building long-term trust through meaningful content. The current scenario does not represent the decline of influencer marketing effectiveness, but rather a crucial turning point. Brands must adopt recalibrated strategies that are aligned with the evolving expectations of the target audiences (Leung et al., 2022). A thoughtful and authentic approach that respects the intelligence and critical awareness of contemporary consumers is essential to guarantee the lasting impact and credibility of influencer marketing in the long term.

Keywords: Influencer marketing, Influencer authenticity, Consumer trust, Influencer credibility, Over-commercialization

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Integrating AI literacy into media education: A tentative curriculum framework for undergraduate communication and business programs - Kamila ALMAZ, Admilson VELOSO DA SILVA (Corvinus University of Budapest, Hungary)

Purpose

Considering AI's growing impact on media systems and the public sphere (Saliu, 2024), this study proposes integrating AI literacy into undergraduate curricula for Communication and Business programs (Kong et al., 2021). Addressing AI as both a technological force and a socio ethical challenge (Wang, et al. 2020; Tiernan, 2023, Saliu, 2024), the paper explores qualitatively how media education can contribute to preparing students for critically engaging with AI-driven media environments (Ng et al, 2021; Ghani, et al. 2025).

Design/methodology/approach

The study applies a qualitative case study approach, combining two methods: a case study approach (Yazan, 2015), analyzing existing AI literacy curricula in English (N=8) retrieved from online databases of educational institutions, which is complemented by semi-structured interviews (Smith, 1995) with university professors and industry experts in AI (N=8). The goal is to identify effective pedagogical strategies and core thematic components for a curriculum that intersects AI and media literacy for undergraduate-level programs in these areas.

(Potential) Findings

The preliminary results demonstrate a lack of sufficient curricula on comprehensive AI literacy, whereby most programs only offer limited exposure to the principles of AI and their impact. Our findings emphasize the necessity of integrating four main types of knowledge: 1) critical thinking, 2) data analysis, 3) algorithmic and basic programming skills, and 4) ethical reflection into media education. The study proposes a tentative curriculum framework that bridges conceptual knowledge with practical skills, empowering students to understand, question, and creatively use AI in communication and business contexts.

Keywords: AI literacy, media education, curriculum design, communication science, digital ethics

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Information, trust, and electoral uncertainty: How Romanians chose their candidates in the cancelled first round of the 2024 presidential election - Antonio AMUZA (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper examines the informational behaviours of Romanian voters during the first round of the 2024 presidential election—an unprecedented electoral moment annulled post-factum by Romania’s Constitutional Court. Using nationally representative survey data (N=572), this study aims to understand the types of media and interpersonal communication that informed voters’ candidate preferences, the role of digital platforms, and how trust in various information sources related to the timing and rationale of vote choice.

Design

The research is based on a post-electoral survey conducted between 26–28 November 2024, shortly before the annulment of the first round. Respondents were asked about their voting behaviour, candidate selection criteria, perceived campaign exposure (TV debates, online ads, direct messaging), and the moment they made their vote decision. The analysis employs descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to identify patterns of information exposure and their relation to political trust, affective alignment, and candidate visibility.

Potential Findings

The findings reveal a fragmented information ecology in which early-deciding voters tend to rely on legacy media and institutional trust, while late-deciding voters are significantly more exposed to political content on TikTok and Facebook. In these algorithmic environments, echo chambers (Sunstein, 2017) and affective publics (Papacharissi, 2015) play a central role in shaping how legitimacy is emotionally perceived and contested. Legitimacy is no longer solely procedural but mediated by symbolic narratives and affective identification (Mouffe, 2000). The data show that exposure to populist messages on digital platforms correlates with voting decisions made closer to election day and with emotional responses of anger or betrayal toward the political system.

Keywords: political communication, Romania 2024 elections, media exposure, trust, vote choice

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Democracy and public deliberations in an AI-mediated world: Navigating utopian potentials and heterotopic tensions - Anca ANTON (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper explores how artificial intelligence (AI) reshapes democratic public deliberations through Michel Foucault's (1984) concepts of *utopia* and *heterotopia*. It examines how AI technologies offer new possibilities for inclusion, transparency, and participatory governance (Landmore, 2024; Tsai et al., 2024), while also posing risks of manipulation, exclusion, and erosion of democratic values (Duberry, 2022; Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). The study aims to critically assess the dual potential of AI as both an enabler of more inclusive democratic practices and a creator of fragmented, exclusionary digital spaces.

Design/methodology/approach

The chapter adopts a critical theoretical approach based on Foucault's (1984) spatial concepts, applying them to contemporary AI applications in democratic contexts. It draws on a range of empirical case studies - including vTaiwan (Computational Democracy Project, 2024), Make.org (Horn & Binder, 2024), Finland's AuroraAI (Menachemson, 2024), and Ukraine's Dozorro (Horn & Binder, 2024) - to illustrate how AI-mediated deliberations manifest utopian aspirations and heterotopic tensions. The analysis integrates insights from communication studies, democratic theory, and technology ethics.

Findings

The findings reveal that AI acts as a double-edged sword in the context of democratic public deliberations. On one hand, AI technologies significantly enhance inclusivity, transparency, and efficiency in democratic processes (Landmore, 2023; Zerfass et al., 2023). Platforms such as vTaiwan and Make.org demonstrate how large-scale citizen engagement can be scaled effectively, facilitating real-time public feedback and informed policymaking. Similarly, AI tools like digital twins and sign language avatars increase accessibility for historically marginalised groups (Horn & Binder, 2024), embodying utopian ideals of broader participation and democratic innovation. On the other hand, the research highlights critical heterotopic tensions arising from AI-mediated spaces. Algorithmic manipulation (Alnemr & Weymouth, 2024), the creation of echo chambers (UNRIC, 2024; Lievrouw, 1998), and diminished human agency present profound risks to the integrity of democratic deliberations. Examples such as Finland's AuroraAI (Räisänen, 2023) and the misuse of AI in electoral campaigns (Bakir, 2020) illustrate how technological interventions, despite aiming for inclusivity, can inadvertently deepen social divides, marginalise minority voices, and compromise transparency. Foucault's (1984) concepts of utopia and heterotopia frame these dynamics, showing that AI technologies simultaneously offer idealistic visions and real-world contradictions within democratic ecosystems.

The study concludes that AI's integration into democratic processes must be critically managed through regulatory frameworks like the EU AI Act (The European Parliament and the European Council, 2024), participatory governance models, and a redefined societal role for communicators (Anton, 2023; Buhmann & Fieseler, 2023). Emphasising transparency, accountability, and ethical design is essential to mitigate AI's heterotopic risks while leveraging its potential to foster more resilient, equitable, and inclusive democratic spaces.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, democracy, public deliberation, utopia, heterotopia

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Algorithms for peace: Ethical dimensions of AI-driven communication strategies in the digital age - Simona BADER, Alexandru-Claudiu RÂȚĂ (West University of Timișoara, Romania)

Purpose

In the age of data-driven communication and personalized outreach, institutions increasingly rely on algorithmic systems and artificial intelligence (AI) to manage their public engagement strategies. This study investigates how such technologies are employed in social impact communication, with a focus on peace promotion campaigns conducted by global institutions. The aim is to critically analyze the ethical implications and strategic value of using AI in message targeting, audience segmentation and content recommendation when the objective is not brand loyalty but cultural change and public good.

Design/Methodology/Approach

The research uses a qualitative method approach: interviews with digital strategists and communication officers from NGOs and international organizations. The study will explore how personalization, real-time analytics and AI-driven targeting are applied or limited by ethical considerations in social campaigns.

Potential Findings

Preliminary findings suggest that algorithmic communication strategies can increase message reach and visibility when aligned with emotionally resonant formats. However, they also risk reinforcing echo chambers or excluding marginalized perspectives due to optimization biases. The study proposes an applied framework for "ethical algorithmic communication", emphasizing transparency, inclusivity and fairness in campaign design. It contributes to expanding the scope of communication theory to include socially driven campaigns that adopt commercial tools for non-commercial goals.

Keywords: digital strategy, ethical marketing, algorithmic personalization, AI in communication, peace campaigns

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New world of journalism: Reconceptualizing the journalism profession in Romania and Moldova - Alexandra BARDAN, Antonia MATEI, Carmen IONESCU, Rodica Melinda ȘUȚU, Bogdan OPREA, Gheorghe ANGHEL, Andrada FISCUTEAN, Natalia VASILENDIUC (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This panel is derived from a forthcoming volume, entitled *Jurnalism sub presiune. O analiză a riscurilor și incertitudinilor profesiei* (Tritonic, 2025), that examines the profound challenges and ongoing transitions shaping journalism in Romania and Moldova. All panel members are contributors to this collective work. Our analysis draws on the third wave of the *Worlds of Journalism Study* (WJS3) and is informed by scholarly discussions around media power, journalistic practices in post-communist contexts, and the interplay of autonomy and structural constraints. These multiple perspectives highlight the wide range of political, economic, technological, and cultural factors currently reshaping the global media sphere (UNESCO, 2021).

Design/methodology/approach

Building on WJS3's methodological framework, the panel utilizes a mix of quantitative survey data and qualitative insights. We explore how political pressures, including shifting regulations and polarization, undermine editorial independence, while economic instability, such as dwindling revenues and precarious labour conditions, heightens uncertainty. Technological advancements broaden the communication landscape yet also exacerbate disinformation risks. Culturally, waning public trust and the proliferation of hate speech complicate journalistic practice. By examining both Romania and Moldova, the panel offers a comparative lens on how journalists adapt strategies to maintain professional roles, safety, and integrity under these layered pressures (Reich & Hanitzsch, 2013).

Findings

Our data suggest that journalists in both contexts are redefining core professional principles to cope with multifaceted risks. Political interference, financial precarity, and digital misinformation converge to challenge traditional models of reporting. Simultaneously, emerging opportunities, such as regional journalistic collaborations, audience engagement through new platforms, and ethical innovation, signal possible paths for resilience. The forthcoming volume will provide a nuanced discussion of these complex developments, underscoring how local cultural legacies intersect with global trends. Ultimately, the panel aims to shed light on how Eastern European journalism can bolster democratic functions and public accountability amid continuous transformation.

Keywords: Journalism practices, digital transformation, risk, Romania, Republic of Moldova

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Always online, always in the field: Politics in the platform ecosystem - Daniele BATTISTA (University of Salerno, Italy)

Abstract

This research project explores the impact of platform society on political communication, with a focus on the *leaderization* of the political arena and the phenomenon of the permanent campaign, both of which are increasingly prominent in today's hybrid media system (Chadwick, 2017; Van Dijck, 2013). The main objective of the study is to analyze how political leaders use social media to establish ongoing forms of engagement with the electorate, strengthen their reputational capital, and contribute to the polarization of public discourse. The central research questions include: How do social media influence the construction of political leadership? What dynamics of disinformation emerge in the context of the permanent campaign? Which digital indicators are relevant for mapping these phenomena? The methodology adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of data gathered through social listening tools (Blogmeter and FanpageKarma) with qualitative interviews conducted with political communication experts and practitioners. The research is structured in three phases: a literature review and methodological framework, empirical investigation of digital dynamics and disinformation risks, and a synthesis of findings with the development of practical recommendations. Five digital indicators will be systematically monitored: engagement, new followers, interactions, sentiment, and the relevance of leader-related keywords. The expected results aim to highlight the correlation between the intensity of leaders' digital presence and continuous intra- and inter-coalitional conflict, often accompanied by disinformation phenomena (Perloff, 2021; Sorensen, 2024). Ultimately, the project seeks to develop guidelines for responsible political communication, promoting transparency and trust in the democratic process (Gili & Panarari, 2020). This contribution aims to enrich academic debate and provide practical tools for better governance of the political-digital ecosystem.

Keywords: Platform Society; Political Leaderization; Permanent Campaign; Digital Disinformation; Social Media Engagement

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Re-evaluating newsworthiness: How Romanian Gen Z's social media habits challenge traditional news values - Adina BAYA (West University of Timișoara, Romania)

Purpose

The proliferation of social media has led to significant transformations in traditional notions of news curation, transferring authority from journalists to user-driven platforms where shareability and virality dominate. This shift has had a profound impact on younger audiences, particularly Gen Z or digital natives, who are at the forefront of these changing habits. For this cohort, social media platforms such as Instagram and TikTok have become primary gateways to news, with the largest part of them considering social media their main source of information. This demographic values speed, accessibility, and engagement, frequently accessing news via curated feeds, trending topics or viral content rather than through deliberate visits to news websites or watching scheduled broadcasts. Our study examines Romanian Gen Z's redefinition of newsworthiness through the lens of Harcup & O'Neill's framework of news values (2017), exploring how criteria such as shareability, viral potential, accessibility and interactivity increasingly compete with canonical principles like proximity or impact. What do young Romanians consider "news"? How do they decide what is trustworthy and newsworthy? And what are the characteristics of their news consumption habits? To tackle these questions, our study reviews how the definition of news values changed over time and asks Romanian Gen Zers to rank traditional principles defining newsworthiness.

Design/methodology/approach

Our study adopts a mixed methods approach, combining focus groups and a survey. The focus groups provided in-depth insights into the preferences and concerns of young Romanians regarding news consumption, with student participants discussing what they consider "news," how they determine trustworthiness, and which stories they find relevant. Complementing these qualitative findings, a survey was distributed to a broader sample of our targeted cohort, gathering quantitative data on their preferred media formats, criteria for selecting the news, trusted sources, and the factors that influence their perception of newsworthiness.

(Potential) Findings

Preliminary findings reveal that Romanian Gen Z blends traditional journalistic criteria defining news values with digital-era expectations. While aligning with frameworks like Harcup & O'Neill's (2017), they also prioritize credibility, fact-checking, and authenticity. This notable finding reflects their heightened awareness of misinformation risks. Their emphasis on visual/emotional appeal and virality underscores social media's influence, while demands for engagement and interactivity signal a shift toward participatory, transparent journalism. The respondents' focus on source transparency and diversity highlights a demand for accurate

yet accessible journalism, though algorithmic preferences for sensational content challenge in-depth reporting. This duality underscores the tension between traditional news values and social media's algorithmic imperatives.

Keywords: News values, Newsworthiness, Romanian Gen Z, Social Media Habits, News Curation.

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***Women journalists, mobile technology and women empowerment in Northern Nigeria* - Susan Alache BELLO (Leeds Beckett University, United Kingdom)**

Purpose

This research focuses on the women journalists, content creators and documentary film makers in Northern Nigeria, how they use mobile technologies to work, if it empowers, and the impact this has on their work and lives. The study seeks to answer the following research questions: 1. What are the challenges faced by women journalists in Northern Nigeria and how do these challenges impact their work? 2. What is role of mobile technology on the work that women journalists do? 3. How has mobile technology empowered women journalists in Northern Nigeria to tell their stories?

Design/methodology/approach

Masculine news-room culture, inequitable pay-gaps and work opportunities between male and female journalists are some of the challenges women journalists encounter, according to literature.(Govender & Muringa, 2025) Little information exists on the utilization of mobile technologies as a tool of empowerment by women in the field of journalism and media content creation. (Ezugwu *et al*, 2025).

The study employs qualitative research approaches of digital ethnography and semi-structured interviews of 17 women. It also examines the views of 5 male managers that own or lead teams in media organizations to get a gendered view on women's use of mobile technology. The data is being systematically coded and categorised with the use of NVivo software to get rich narratives from the participants.

Drawing on African Technocultural Feminist Theory (ATFT) which examines the intersection of technology and the practice of culture amongst African technology users and their approach to new media technology (Enyinnaya & Arthur, 2024), my research seeks to explore issues around marginalisation of access stemming from gender and cultural restrictions and how women negotiate power and positionality using mobile technology.

(Potential) Findings

Initial findings indicate that women have a difficult time accessing mobile technology, equipment and accessories like editing software and internet connection to work with. They struggle to adapt to these technologies, social and cultural environments remain inconducive for women to thrive at work but are resilient and determined to overcome barriers by developing themselves, moving the boundaries of technical knowledge required for expertise and setting up structures to educate and empower other women. This research has the potential to address issues around government policies regarding technology education and access for women, improve socio-cultural and working environments and highlight the need to focus on mentorship programs around technology use in the media and journalism sector.

It will contribute to academic literature on journalism, women/gender studies by identifying the challenges women in the field face and proposing solutions.

Keywords: Mobile Technology, Women Journalists, Northern Nigeria, Content Creators, Digital Ethnography

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Bought attention: Media and propaganda expenditure in Romania's May 2025 presidential elections. Political advertising, editorial risk, and the fragile economy of journalism - Loredana BERTIȘAN-POP (Babeș-Bolyai University, Romania)

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to examine how political campaign expenditure under the category “media and propaganda” influences the structure, independence, and financial sustainability of the media industry in Romania. In a context marked by low public trust (Meza 2020), journalism in Romania faces increasing pressure from both political and economic forces (Day, Otto & Simion, 2025). This research contributes to ongoing debates about media transparency, political communication, and the evolving relationship between political actors and the press. Focusing on the Romanian presidential elections from May 2025, the study analyzes official campaign expenses reported by candidates to the Permanent Electoral Authority (AEP) on media. The research addresses several questions: To what extent does political financing support Romanian media? Which types of media benefit most from these funds? What long-term effects might this financial dependency have on media pluralism and journalistic autonomy?

The study argues that media spending during campaigns has become more than just a tool for political electoral promotion, but it functions as an informal subsidy for parts of the media landscape. This creates ethical and structural challenges, particularly when newsrooms rely on campaign revenues to sustain themselves. The findings aim to contribute to a solution for the urgent need for sustainable funding models that preserve editorial independence and journalistic integrity in fragile democracies.

Design/methodology/approach

This mixed-methods study combines quantitative analysis of financial disclosures with qualitative interpretation of media dynamics. The core dataset consists of official AEP reports from all candidates in the May 2025 elections, focusing on the “media and propaganda” expenditure category. Qualitatively, the study contextualizes these patterns within Romania’s broader media ecosystem. It draws on journalistic investigations, public records, and existing academic literature to assess how campaign financing affects editorial independence and newsroom behavior. The methodology ensures a nuanced understanding of how political money circulates within, and potentially distorts, the information landscape.

(Potential) Findings

A key insight is that campaign financing has evolved into a mechanism for subsidizing media outlets. This financial influx, however, is not neutral: it often reinforces dependency relationships, raising concerns about the editorial independence of the beneficiary media. The research underscores the urgent need for developing alternative funding mechanisms

that support journalism without compromising its integrity. The timing of this research is particularly relevant, as it is being discussed only one month after the presidential elections, a moment when public attention is still actively engaged with the outcomes and processes of the campaign. Presenting this study in such close proximity to the elections allows for an immediate, evidence-based reflection on how campaign financing influenced media practices and visibility during the electoral period. Moreover, it provides a critical opportunity to inform post-election debates around transparency, electoral fairness, and the role of media in democratic processes, while these issues are still being discussed in both public and institutional arenas.

Keywords: campaign, money, financing, media outlets

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Journalists and Daily Life: Professional Risks and Biographical Ruptures - Giacomo BUONCOMPAGNI (University of Macerata, Italy)

Purpose

Journalists, who find themselves at the center of mass communication and an interconnected society, are often invisible in their professional and daily life practices.

In an era in which journalism is under more pressure than ever – between the acceleration of news, the intensification of digital competition and the growing distrust of audiences – it is essential to understand the human side of this profession (Splendore, 2017; Tandoc, Takahashi 2018.; Splendore, Sorrentino, 2022; Buoncompagni, 2024a, 2024b).

Through the biographies of journalists, we will retrace their days, the choices, the doubts, the defeats and the victories that have defined them as people first and then as information professionals.

By exploring the daily lives of journalists, we will try to answer four main research questions. How do you balance the need for truth with the pressures of the information market? How do you face ethical challenges in an ever-changing context? What is the price, sometimes invisible, that journalists pay to report what happens in the world? How much do family, one's health and domestic economy influence the organization of one's professional life?

Design/methodology/approach

This work therefore aims to explore the daily experiences of journalists, focusing on how their personal, professional and social lives are shaped by the profession they practice. From a methodological point of view, a qualitative approach was chosen, with the aim of understanding the complexity of the individual experiences of journalists, analyzing their stories through a (sociological) perspective that takes into account historical, social, cultural and psychological factors.

The methodology adopted is divided into different phases, from direct interviews to biographical research, through the analysis of the contents produced and the comparison with contemporary sociological theories (Tejedor, 2009; Cardano, 2011; Corbetta, 2015; Prados et. Al., 2017).

(Potential) Findings

The methodology adopted, integrating biographical analysis, interviews, participant observation and content analysis, has allowed us to grasp a multifaceted vision of contemporary journalism. We have tried to go beyond the mere technical dimension of the profession to reveal the human, emotional and social side of those who, every day, commit themselves to telling the world, often at the cost of immeasurable personal sacrifices. Ultimately, this work wants to be a tribute to those professionals who, despite the difficulties, continue to bear witness to reality with courage and passion. Journalism, in its essence, is an act of resistance, a commitment to the truth and the responsibility to give voice to those who

cannot speak. The stories told here remind us that, behind every news story and every reportage, there is a life made of choices, transformations and hopes - and that, in this intertwining of existences, the value of information lies precisely in the ability to humanize the world.

Keywords: journalism; media; stories; news; daily life

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C

Increase engagement in learning through online Facebook groups – Study case of students in communication sciences - Oana-Maria CĂLIN (University of Bucharest, Romania)

In the current landscape of higher education, digital platforms—particularly Facebook groups—have emerged as significant tools in supporting educational processes, especially within the field of communication studies. This study investigates the pedagogical potential of Facebook groups, grounded in key theoretical frameworks such as collaborative learning (Vygotsky, 1978), social learning theory (Bandura, 2001), digital learning environments (Anderson & Dron, 2011), and the concept of communities of practice (Wenger, 2002). The research focuses on Facebook groups established between 2019 and 2024, designed to facilitate the teaching of project management courses for undergraduate students in communication programs. Utilizing Facebook’s built-in analytics tools alongside content analysis methodology (Krippendorff, 2004), the study identifies the nature of interactions among group members and the collaborative learning strategies employed.

The study’s objectives (1) to examine the dynamics of online academic interaction with attention to collaboration, instructor involvement, and academic outcomes; (2) to identify specific characteristics of academic communities of practice as manifested in Facebook learning groups; and (3) to evaluate the extent to which these groups function as integral components of the educational process. Findings suggest that Facebook groups offer a potentially effective environment for collaborative learning by fostering engagement and enhancing interest in academic topics. However, they also pose challenges, including digital dependency and a decreasing level of student engagement with the Facebook platform itself. The study concludes with a set of principles and recommendations applicable to the integration of any digital platform into academic learning environments.

Keywords: Facebook groups, collaborative learning, communication studies, communities of practice, digital education, social learning, higher education.

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TikTok, distrust in legacy media, and the crystallization of populist political preferences: Qualitative insights from Romanian users - Alexandra CODĂU, Valentin VANGHELESCU (Ovidius University of Constanța, Romania)

Purpose

Habermas's ideal of a rational, egalitarian public sphere (1989) - one in which everyone could, at least in theory, participate in collective debate - has eroded in the digital age. Digital platforms privilege rapid, emotional exchanges over deliberation (Castells, 2012) and splinter discourse into myriad private micro-spheres aimed at self-validation rather than consensus (Papacharissi, 2010). Algorithms amplify these fractures by cultivating echo chambers and polarisation (Sunstein, 2017), social networks accelerate disinformation and radicalisation (Benkler, 2018), and surveillance capitalism exploits personal data (Zuboff, 2019) to steer both consumer and political behaviour, widening the gap between democratic ideals and digital realities. In this context, social media have become fertile ground for the rise of populist politicians. Populism is a thin-centred ideology that glorifies "ordinary people" while denouncing a "corrupt elite," presenting society as two uniform, antagonistic camps (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2017). Rooted in this dichotomy, it insists that legitimate politics should bypass entrenched establishments and offer direct, unfiltered expression of the people's *volonté générale* (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2017). Building on these theoretical insights, the present study examines how citizens distance themselves from legacy media and cultivate TikTok as a credible source of information on elections and political issues.

Design/methodology/approach

We employ a qualitative research design, conducting structured interviews with a heterogeneous sample of Romanian TikTok users from the Dobrogea region. Participants were selected to capture variation in age, social background, usage frequency, and platform practices. In our study, we address two research questions: RQ1. *How does TikTok shape the relationship between users and political actors?* RQ2. *What role does TikTok play in forming or strengthening users' affinity toward those political actors?*

(Potential) Findings

Our working hypothesis is that TikTok users who gravitate toward populist political actors exhibit low trust in legacy media and perceive TikTok content as more credible, authentic, and relevant to their political interests.

Keywords: digital public sphere, TikTok, legacy media, social media, populism

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Mic check: Celebrities, social media, and political discourse in the Romanian presidential campaign - Alexandru CONDRACHE (West University of Timișoara, Romania)

In the context of the Romanian presidential elections, social media has become a powerful tool not only for political candidates but also for cultural influencers and celebrities who shape public opinion. This paper explores the role of pop culture figures - specifically actors and musicians with significant online visibility - in shaping political discourse and voter perception through social media during the 2024 presidential campaign. The focus is on the period following the first round of elections, a time marked by increased polarization and intensified public engagement.

Through a qualitative and quantitative content analysis, this study investigates how high-profile celebrities such as Adrian Văncică and Delia Matache (anti-Georgescu) and Connect-R and Culiță Sterp (pro-Georgescu) used their platforms to express political opinions, mobilize audiences, and react to the outcomes of the first electoral round. The research examines their public posts on platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook, analyzing both the content of their messages - ranging from satire and criticism to open endorsement and nationalistic rhetoric - and the patterns of audience interaction they generated.

Each celebrity is considered not only in terms of the message they shared but also in relation to their follower base, average engagement rates (likes, comments, shares), and the sentiment of responses received. For example, Delia Matache's ironic and openly critical commentary on nationalist politics and disinformation sparked intense debate, while Connect-R's posts highlighted unity and identity, aligning more closely with Georgescu's ideological messaging. Culiță Sterp's support for Georgescu combined populist themes with personal narratives that resonated with his fanbase.

This study reveals the complex and sometimes contradictory ways in which pop culture personalities influence the political landscape, highlighting their dual role as both entertainers and informal opinion leaders. By examining their messages, reach, and audience engagement, the paper contributes to understanding the mediatized nature of contemporary political communication and the blurred lines between cultural and political authority in the digital age.

Keywords: pop culture, social media, presidential campaign, celebrity endorsement, public opinion

Legitimising student voices: Discursive strategies in Romanian youth organisations' digital activism - Anastasia COSTE (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper investigates how two major Romanian national student organisations—one representing high school students (The National Council of Students) and the other, university students (The National Alliance of Student Organisations in Romania)—employ legitimisation strategies to position themselves as credible civic actors in digital activism. Focusing on Facebook, the most widely used social media platform in Romania, the study investigates how these organisations construct discursive authority, particularly during socio-political disruption such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the onset of the war in Ukraine, and national reforms affecting youth. Romania has a strong tradition of student participation in social movements, yet the digital transformation of activism poses new challenges and opportunities for how student voices are represented and legitimised in public discourse.

Design/methodology/approach

The research draws on the legitimisation framework developed by Van Leeuwen & Wodak (1999) and further adapted by Vaara et al. (2006), which includes strategies such as normalisation, authorisation, rationalisation, moral evaluation, and narrativisation. In addition, this study incorporates the perspective of *destructive legitimisation* as conceptualised by Vestergaard & Uldam (2022), focusing on two key delegitimation strategies: *deauthorisation* and *demoralisation*. These categories capture how organisations challenge opposing positions or actors by questioning their authority or moral standing. The empirical corpus consists of Facebook posts published from 2019 to 2022 by the two national organisations, selected based on post frequency related to activism initiatives. A qualitative content analysis was conducted to identify recurring legitimisation and delegitimation patterns and the context in which they emerge.

(Potential) Findings

The analysis is expected to reveal how Romanian student organisations legitimise their activism in digital spaces, especially during periods of political uncertainty and public crisis. Particular attention is given to how these organisations position themselves as credible intermediaries between youth and decision-makers, often invoking moral authority, institutional recognition, or the urgency of student needs. By focusing on digital discourse, the study seeks to understand how legitimisation is performed and negotiated in the online public sphere. This research contributes to ongoing debates on youth participation, political communication, and the evolving nature of activism in post-pandemic, post-socialist democracies.

Keywords

Student organisations, legitimation, digital activism, Romania, youth participation

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D

From temple to screen: the presence of the sacred in Romanian trap culture - Liviu-Andrei DOBRE (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper presents the presence of religious and spiritual aspects in the music of some of the top Romanian trap artists, taking into account both lyrics and videos available on platforms such as YouTube - materials that can be promoted in the digital environment.

Through this study, the aim is to show how religious and spiritual elements are evoked, within a music that is recognized for its underlying nihilism, states of ecstasy, but also states of depression (Kaluža, 2018).

Methodology

As research questions, they are the following: are there religious and/or spiritual mentions in Romanian trap music? If so, what are they? Do the visual materials complement or not the lyrics and constructed identities?

The corpus is represented by the songs and albums of popular Romanian trap artists, according to Spotify (2023). In terms of methodology, for the content analysis of the lyrics, the categories of Knott & Poole (2016) are used, as well as the semiotic analysis of the visual representations of the videos (Curtin, 2009).

Potential findings

An anticipated outcome is that trap artists, like hip-hop artists in general, use religious and spiritual aspects to construct their identities (Hall, 2011) and their lyrics (Miller, 2015; Macon, 2017), but also to rebel against dominant culture (Clarke, Hall, Jefferson & Roberts, 2005; Hebdige, 1979).

This analysis offers insights into the mix between the profane and the sacred (Dyson, 2002; Hodge, 2010), a mix that becomes present not only in headphones or at concerts, but also online, where it can be available not only to the targeted audience, but also to the general public.

Keywords: Romanian trap, sacred and profane, digital culture

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***Harnessing AI in the Romanian newsrooms* - Georgeta DRULĂ (University of Bucharest, Romania)**

Purpose

The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) has put pressure on the media business (Opdahl et al., 2023). The complexity of AI adoption in newsrooms brings into debate many aspects of news production, such as the public's perception and acceptance of AI-generated content, internal difficulties related to limited resources for AI technologies implementation, and ethical and safety standards around AI use - are just some of them (Parratt-Fernández et al., 2024; Amponsah & Atianashie, 2024).

The use of AI in newsrooms is studied with two approaches: the news production process perspective (Sirén-Heikel et al., 2022; de-Lima-Santos & Salaverría, 2021) and the perspective of news consumption and audience (Graefe & Bohlken, 2020). All the controversies related to the adoption of AI in newsrooms have started to have more and more solutions to solve doubtful situations.

This research highlights the level of interest of Romanian journalists and the use of AI tools for various tasks in newsrooms. It explores the implications of AI and its potential in news production. The research is based on interviews with media professionals about AI harnessing in newsrooms.

Methodology

The study examines how Romanian newsrooms engage with AI, a phenomenon anticipated to transform journalism's future.

These technologies raise many important aspects regarding the production of news.

The current work reflects Romanian newsrooms' interest in using AI tools for automation processes.

This research is based on interviews with 13 journalists and media professionals from Romanian newsrooms. The interviews highlight the interest in utilizing AI tools for professional tasks.

The research questions are:

RQ1: What uses do AI tools have or could have in the newsroom, and are pointed out by Romanian journalists?

RQ2: What concerns about using AI tools in the newsroom are pointed out by Romanian journalists?

RQ3: What AI tools are currently used in journalistic tasks and processes in newsrooms?

This study applies mixed methods of qualitative data analysis.

Findings

The conclusions indicate a growing interest in integrating AI into Romanian newsrooms. Journalists in Romania report that AI is particularly useful in the pre-production and post-

production phases of news production. It helps them complete tasks more quickly while still under human control. They emphasize that the core responsibility of creating news remains with them, with no reliance on algorithmic involvement for the creative process.

Keywords: AI in newsroom, automated journalism, AI in news production, robot journalism

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F

Perception and use of algorithmic recommendation systems on the Internet among future media professionals: Do we understand and communicate with algorithms? - Irina FILIPOVIĆ, Ilija MILOSAVLJEVIĆ (University of Niš, Serbia)

Purpose

The hyperproduction of content and the hyperactivity of users in the digital world have created a need to systematize this space through various algorithmic analyses of big user data and content personalization (Xia et al, 2022). Although algorithmic systems appear to serve easier navigation in the online sphere, they primarily operate with the aim of personalized strategic communication, built on marketing logic (Thirumagal et al, 2024; Napoli, 2014), steering attention and preferences, justified by the "tyranny of choice" (Salecl, 2011). By tracking users' activities, habits, and affinities—through cookies, big data, and search history—algorithmic systems determine the content presented to users (Pariser, 2011). However, users remain only superficially aware of these mechanisms, recognizing them mostly through personal experience, due to a lack of adequate information and systematic education (Mierzejewska, 2021), and rarely engage in active "communication" with algorithms. Since journalism and communication students, due to the nature of their studies, possess above-average knowledge of digital trends, the aim of this research is to examine how this group perceives algorithmic recommendation systems and how their understanding of these systems affects their behavior online.

Design/methodology/approach

The main hypothesis of the research states that *Journalism and communication students have a positive perception of algorithmic recommendation systems online, understand how they work, and actively engage in "training" the algorithm to best suit their needs.* A specifically designed questionnaire is used, comprising two parts: one focused on demographic data and internet usage habits, and the other on attitudes toward algorithmic recommendation systems and related activities. The analysis applies both qualitative and quantitative methods, using Pearson's chi-square test via SPSS 22.0 to explore correlations and statistical significance. Data collection will take place in April and May 2025 through Google Forms, with an expected sample size of N=200.

(Potential) Findings

It is anticipated that the main hypothesis will be confirmed, revealing a statistically significant difference between senior students, who demonstrate a better understanding of the digital world, and junior students. The research is also expected to identify the most common

methods for "training" algorithmic recommendation systems, strategies for resisting unwanted content, and privacy protection habits in the digital environment.

Keywords: Algorithmic Recommendation Systems, Content, Personalization, Digital Literacy, Strategic Communication, Attention Management

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G

Between Screens and Dreams: Emotional Attachments, Identity, and Parasocial Bonds in Romanian K-pop Fan Culture - Mihai-Claudiu GAVRILESCU, Sonia-Maria LUNGU (SNSPA, Romania)

Purpose

This paper investigates how parasocial relationships (PSRs) shape the emotional lives, media practices, and identity development of Romanian Gen Z fans engaged with K-pop culture. Building on recent scholarship that highlights the complexity and ambivalence of PSRs in digital environments (Reinikainen et al., 2020; Flinchum et al., 2024), the study explores how young fans develop affective bonds with media avatars, interact with platforms designed to simulate intimacy (e.g., Bubble), and construct personal and social identities within fandom communities. The research is situated within the broader context of the K-pop industry's highly curated idol-fan ecosystem (Huang, 2024), where aspirational narratives and algorithmic engagement sustain long-term parasocial attachments. Key themes include the perceived authenticity of idols, the emotional benefits of PSRs, and how digital intimacy is interpreted and negotiated by fans.

Methodology

The study employs a qualitative design based on in-depth, semi-structured interviews with 15 Romanian K-pop fans aged 16 to 25. Participants were recruited through purposive sampling to ensure variation in fandom intensity and emotional involvement. The interviews addressed three core questions: (1) What are the main media consumption patterns of Romanian youth related to K-pop? (2) What emotional and social factors facilitate the formation of PSRs? (3) What are the perceived impacts of these relationships on well-being, daily life, and self-concept? Data were analyzed thematically using grounded theory techniques, enabling an inductive approach to meaning-making. The analysis foregrounds fans' subjective experiences, emotional investments, and the identity work embedded in their fandom participation.

Findings

Results indicate a dual structure in media use: platforms like Instagram, Twitter (X), and YouTube enable direct access to idols, while TikTok and fan-created content support community engagement. The Bubble app is considered the most intimate medium, though usage is limited by doubts about its authenticity. Participants with strong emotional bonds to idols view PSRs as important sources of comfort, motivation, and self-worth. These relationships are often maintained through ritualized media practices—daily check-ins, aesthetic emulation, and idol-inspired self-improvement. PSRs are described as emotionally

stable compared to offline relationships, though most fans demonstrate awareness of their one-sided nature. Identity alignment, aspirational mimicry, and peer bonding within fan communities play key roles in sustaining these attachments.

The study offers practical insights for youth-focused digital policy, media literacy, and platform governance. While PSRs can foster self-esteem and resilience, there is a need for proactive strategies to mitigate emotional overdependence. Educational and digital well-being initiatives should promote critical awareness of parasocial dynamics, supporting young users in maintaining healthy emotional boundaries in fan environments.

Keywords: Parasocial relationships, K-pop fandom, emotional attachment, Gen Z, identity, digital intimacy

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Mobile Journalism Practice and Education in Central-East European Countries - Rita GLÓZER (University of Pécs, Hungary), Nataliia NECHAIEVA-YURIICHUK (Yuriy Fed'kovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine), Anna SÁMELOVÁ (Comenius University Bratislava, Slovakia), Gheorghe ANGHEL, Iulian VEGHEȘ, Anamaria NEAGU (University of Bucharest, Romania), Özge SOMLYAI (Eötvös Loránd University, Hungary)

Purpose

This panel originates from an international research project titled *Mobile Journalism Practice and Education in Central-East European Countries*. The project explores the emergence, integration, and perception of mobile journalism (mojo) across 15 countries in the region, including Romania. All panel participants are involved in the project, either as country coordinators or contributors. The research addresses the transformative potential of mojo in journalistic workflows, media education, and professional cultures within post-socialist and transitional democracies. By providing a multi-actor, cross-national perspective, the panel aims to uncover how technological innovation intersects with institutional, educational, and generational dynamics in shaping the future of mobile journalism in Central and Eastern Europe.

Design/methodology/approach

The study employs quantitative methodologies, using a structured questionnaire administered to journalists, students, and academic staff (with over 100 respondents per country), followed by semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire addresses six key dimensions: practice, education, technology use, production, post-production, and demographic context. Responses are analyzed both nationally and comparatively. The second phase of the project involves interviews with selected participants to deepen the understanding of attitudes toward mobile journalism (mojo) and its practical and pedagogical implications. The panel will present early insights from this data, including generational divides in technology adoption, challenges in curriculum integration, and varying levels of institutional support or resistance to mojo practices.

Findings

Preliminary results suggest significant variance in mojo adoption across the region, influenced by factors such as technological infrastructure, and professional cultures. While younger journalists and students often embrace mobile-first approaches, educators and legacy media actors display more cautious or skeptical attitudes. Despite challenges—ranging from lack of equipment and training to institutional inertia—mobile journalism is increasingly seen as a tool for adaptability, storytelling innovation, and resourceful reporting in underfunded media

systems. The panel will reflect on the implications of these findings for journalism education reform, newsroom transformation, and regional collaboration, and propose actionable strategies for embedding mojo in both practice and pedagogy.

Keywords: mobile journalism, digital journalism, education, practice

Between diagnosis and intervention: The phenomenon of disinformation from the perspective of communication professionals - Gabriela GUIU, Georgiana UDREA, Simina BUCULEI (SNSPA, Romania)

Scop

În contextul digital actual, marcat de *dezordine* informațională, polarizare și neîncredere în instituții, granițele dintre ficțiune și realitate devin permeabile, spațiul public fiind populat cu narațiuni manipulative, actori informaționali obscuri și tehnologii care simulează realitatea cu o fidelitate tot mai greu de detectat (Harris, 2025; Saeidnia et al., 2025). Într-un peisaj digital dominat de algoritmi, conținut generat automat și viralizare accelerată, înțelegerea fenomenului dezinformării presupune o analiză integrată a intenționalității, canalelor de difuzare și efectelor sociale (Santos, 2023). Astfel, acest fenomen a intensificat preocupările din partea specialiștilor cu privire la efecte, modul în care funcționează și se propagă la nivelul societății. Această lucrare își propune să investigheze modul în care specialiștii în comunicare din România (actori cu rol-cheie în formularea și implementarea strategiilor de comunicare publică) definesc, interpretează și evaluează fenomenul dezinformării, cu scopul de a identifica principalele vulnerabilități ale spațiului informațional și de a evalua eficienței măsurilor de combatere.

Metodologie

Pentru atingerea obiectivelor, s-a optat pentru o abordare calitativă, bazată pe interviuri semi-structurate, realizate cu 25 de specialiști în comunicare activi în domeniul academic, instituțional sau mediatic. Interviurile au urmărit trei direcții principale: definirea fenomenului și identificarea mecanismelor de propagare; evaluarea efectelor dezinformării în plan individual, social și politic, precum și aprecierea eficienței strategiilor actuale de combatere, cu accent pe rolul educației media și al platformelor digitale.

Rezultate

Participanții definesc dezinformarea prin prisma intenționalității, accentuând caracterul strategic al difuzării de informații false în scopuri ideologice, economice sau politice. Rețelele sociale *online* sunt considerate principalul canal de propagare, un rol important în facilitarea viralizării conținutului înșelător fiind atribuit algoritmilor, camerelor de rezonanță și bulelor de filtrare. Efectele identificate sunt multiple: de la anxietate informațională, scăderea încrederii în instituții și polarizare ideologică la efecte în sfera sănătății publice și destabilizarea proceselor democratice. Cu referire la metodele de combatere a fenomenului, *fact-checking*-ul și reglementările instituționale sunt văzute ca măsuri eficiente pe termen scurt, în timp ce educația media este percepută drept cea mai potrivită soluție pe termen lung, prin intervenții sistemice, care să combine măsuri educaționale, tehnice și legislative. Concluziile sugerează că politicile publice viitoare ar trebui să includă dezvoltarea unor

programe integrate de alfabetizare media, introducerea competențelor de evaluare critică a informațiilor în curricula școlară, precum și o regândire a responsabilităților platformelor digitale în combaterea dezinformării. Cercetarea poate reprezenta un suport empiric pentru crearea unor mecanisme funcționale de protejare a cetățenilor în fața conținutului manipulativ.

Cuvinte-cheie: dezinformare, experți în comunicare, rețele sociale *online*, educație media

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H

The geopolitics of digital space: From data territories to digital sovereignty and back to digital colonialism - Jasmin HASANOVIĆ (University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)

Purpose

This paper aims to critically explore the evolving relationship between geopolitics and how it is being transformed in the era of intensified technological interdependence. It seeks to understand how new power relations of technological empires, Big-Tech corporations in the first place, reshape sovereign authority by extracting data and controlling digital infrastructures, traditionally tied to territorial boundaries. Understanding data territories as new geopolitical spaces highlights the emergence of contested digital spatialities, where geopolitical struggles are increasingly shifting to digital realms. In these spaces, both nation-states and major technology corporations act as key players, challenging and redefining the notions of sovereignty.

Design/methodology/approach

The study draws on a conceptual analysis based on a critical theoretical approach that integrates political science, political philosophy, and digital studies. It begins by re-examining the historical notion of sovereignty and its contemporary reinterpretations within digital contexts. It then conceptualizes digital spatiality by investigating how data relations serve as new forms of power relations. It also employs a qualitative methodology and a comparative examination of different state strategies (China, the US, the EU) regarding digital sovereignty, alongside an analysis of how corporate practices contribute to the phenomenon of digital colonialism.

Findings

The paper anticipates that the geopolitics of the digital realm reveals a fragmented and multiversed sovereignty, characterized by overlapping and competing claims by states and corporations. It identifies a new form of digital colonialism where data and profits flow unidirectionally – primarily benefiting tech giants while exploiting human and natural resources in the Global South. Furthermore, it shows that while digital technologies are often framed as instruments of empowerment, they simultaneously reinforce existing global inequalities and introduce new forms of dependency and domination. The study highlights that any meaningful pursuit of digital sovereignty must address not only regulatory control but also the underlying economic and material structures of digital technology production and distribution.

Keywords: Geopolitics, Digital Sovereignty, Data Territories, Digital Colonialism

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The Georgescu naming game, Romania, November 2024 - March 2025 - Eugen ISTODOR (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Between November 2024 and March 2025, Romania experienced a series of social movements that emerged primarily online and aligned with the anthropology of naming. These events culminated in the surprising success of Călin Georgescu, a largely unknown candidate who campaigned almost exclusively on TikTok and declared himself the “chosen one of the Romanian people” and an “anti-system” figure, citing zero campaign expenditures. The political establishment responded too late and with confusion, while only some parts of the mainstream media attempted to construct a public identity for Georgescu. In this vacuum, his supporters elevated him to the status of a messianic figure. His success in reaching the final round of the presidential election became a performative act, coinciding with theoretical frameworks such as J.L. Austin’s ‘doing things with words,’ Mary Douglas’s ‘purity and danger,’ and identity binaries like ‘known–unknown’ and ‘ours–outsider.’ These frameworks shaped spontaneous strategies for defending or discrediting the candidate.

The online campaign rapidly transformed into a broader public confrontation, incorporating identity construction (Levi-Strauss), descent theory (Schneider, Howell, Bloch), and the codification of Georgescu’s image as a savior. Bourdieu’s and Foucault’s theories on symbolic violence and the power of naming were evident in radical messages from his supporters and isolationist leaders. The research methodology combined social media monitoring, analysis of mainstream media, and face-to-face interviews with both ‘sovereignist’ and ‘progressive’ participants. A multidisciplinary approach guided the study, drawing from behavioral psychology, multimedia communication, and anthropology. The role of mainstream media in legitimizing or delegitimizing Georgescu contributed evidence used by state institutions to consider banning his candidacy in May 2025.

This paper highlights the volatile intersection of digital media, political identity, and performative language within Romania’s evolving democratic landscape.

Keywords: digital politics, performative language, identity construction, symbolic power, Romanian elections.

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Heart or hardware? Mapping user engagement through Samsung's emotional and rational messaging - Roland ÎMPUȘCATU (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This study explores how Samsung, one of the most influential technology brands on social media, strategically employs text-based communication on Facebook during its 2024 product launches. Given Samsung's dominant online presence, the research investigates whether the company relies more heavily on rational or emotional appeals in its messaging and how these approaches correlate with user engagement behaviors, specifically likes, shares, and comments. The objective is to assess which communication style generates higher engagement, offering insights into the effectiveness of content strategies in the digital marketing ecosystem.

Design/methodology/approach

The study utilizes a keyword-driven scraping tool to extract Facebook posts related to Samsung's major 2024 product lines (e.g., #GalaxyAI, #AITV, "Galaxy", "Bespoke"). The analysis is conducted in three stages:

1. Post Frequency Analysis – Identifies the products most frequently promoted by Samsung, allowing us to map their strategic communication priorities.
2. Appeal Classification – Posts are coded to determine whether the dominant message is rational (e.g., technical specifications, pricing, functionality) or emotional (e.g., lifestyle, excitement, inspiration).
3. Engagement Correlation – Using one-way ANOVA with Post-Hoc Tukey tests, the study statistically examines the relationship between appeal type and user interaction patterns (likes, comments, shares), to evaluate which style fosters deeper engagement.

This methodology provides both a quantitative and qualitative understanding of the brand's communication performance.

(Potential) Findings

Preliminary hypotheses suggest that Samsung will favor a rational appeal strategy, consistent with its technological positioning. This includes emphasis on utility-based arguments such as device performance, hardware features, and innovation (Bali et al., 2023). Furthermore, it is anticipated that rational messaging will elicit higher engagement metrics, especially in the form of likes and comments, than emotional appeals. These findings align with previous social media research indicating that for tech brands, information-rich content tends to drive more

substantial audience interaction (Kim & Yang, 2017; Saxton & Waters, 2014). The study contributes to the broader understanding of how message framing in digital platforms can influence consumer behavior in the context of high-tech product marketing.

Keywords: Samsung, social media marketing, Facebook communication, user engagement, digital advertising

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J

Political Branding in the Age of Social Media: The Case of Trump/Musk Interview on X - Habiba JOUINI (University of Sfax, Tunisia)

Social media platforms have fundamentally transformed the way how politicians communicate with their audience, present their agenda, and brand their political identity. Taking the case of Donald Trump's return to the platform X, this study is interested in how he seized the opportunity to address millions of social media followers in what he calls "the biggest interview in history". The interview took place via X platform in an attempt to rebrand Trump's political persona during the 2024 election campaign. It represents an interesting case where the political actor, media outlet, and corporate platform merged together despite of Musk's attempt to reposition the platform as a free speech alternative to mainstream media. Drawing on the theoretical frameworks of political branding (Lee-Marshment, 2001), networked populism (Moffitt, 2016), and mediatization (Hjarvard, 2008; Stromback, 2008), this paper analyzes how Trump strategically adapted his communication style, and populist messaging to fit the logics of the X platform and the expectations of its user base. It also questions Musk's role as platform owner and interviewer, and the implications of this on neutrality, gatekeeping, and political legitimacy.

The paper adopts qualitative content analysis approach to study the interview transcript, and user engagement metrics. It argues that Trump's appearance on X represent a deliberate rebranding effort shifting from the aggressive persona of previous campaigns to a more media savvy image, while still adopting core populist themes.

Keywords: Political branding, social media, Populism, 2024 election, mediatization

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K

From narrative to reality: The evolution of immersiveness in advertising - Aikaterini KATSOTA (Universidade Católica Portuguesa, Portugal), Alexandre DUARTE (ICNOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal)

Purpose

This article aims to trace the evolution of advertising from linear, one-way storytelling to immersive, technology-driven experiences. As storytelling has evolved into a scientifically recognized branding tool (Duarte & Soeiro, 2025), with the power to capture attention and generate vivid mental images (Green, 2021), narrative ads, by combining emotional and persuasive elements, improve brand perception and emotional engagement (Lundqvist et al., 2013).

As the digital environment evolves, storytelling has shifted from brand-controlled monologues to dynamic, consumer-driven dialogues (Herskovitz & Crystal, 2010).

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) enrich this shift, transforming passive spectators into active participants through interactive formats rich in sensory resources (Chen & Yao, 2022). This greater interactivity not only increases message retention but also reshapes the entire advertiser-consumer relationship (Alcañiz et al., 2019).

Design/methodology/approach

Theoretical exploration of concepts.

(Potential) Findings

Positioned as the next frontier, the Metaverse is uniting telepresence and narrative transportation in an unprecedented state of cognitive and emotional engagement. This space allows for persistent and personalized interaction with brand content, where traditional advertising loses ground to experiential storytelling (Chen & Yao, 2022). These virtual environments increase brand visibility and promote loyalty through continuous and immersive engagement (Kim et al., 2017). However, this future-shaping technology also brings significant concerns, such as media addiction, user privacy, and psychological well-being.

Storytelling in advertising has evolved from emotional narratives in traditional media to immersive, multi-sensory experiences enabled by new technologies such as the Metaverse. This evolution signals a paradigm shift in advertising, where engagement, interactivity, and immersion are no longer optional enhancements but essential components for capturing attention and building meaningful brand relationships in an ever-expanding digital landscape.

Keywords: Storytelling, immersive advertising, augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), metaverse.

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L

The availability of resources as power element in the internal institutionalization of the communication function within Latvian state direct administration institutions - Inga LATKOVSKA (University of Latvia, Latvia), Ieva ZAUMANE (Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences, Latvia)

Abstract

The study aims to examine how the power aspect of the internal institutionalization of the communication function—namely, the access to technological, human, and financial resources—is ensured in Latvia’s state direct administration institutions, and to analyze the influence of resource availability on strategic communication within these institutions. The analysis was conducted using a mixed-methods research strategy. Data were obtained from two sources: (1) an online survey with 76 respondents; and (2) 56 in-depth interviews with both communication specialists and Heads of institutions.

The results indicate that limited resource availability poses a significant challenge in public administration, impacting three core areas: (1) Limited financial capacity constrains the full implementation of the communication function. Many institutions lack dedicated budgets to support communication campaigns, particularly in digital and social media environments. (2) Access to communication technology is largely determined by institutional budgets, often necessitating the outsourcing of services such as media monitoring and design. Financial constraints also limit the adoption of advanced software tools, hindering the implementation of efficient and high-quality communication practices. (3) Staffing limitations further impede the communication function. Employees are frequently overburdened, which increases the risk of burnout. This situation is exacerbated by the lack of financial and technological support, placing additional pressure on communication personnel.

Keywords: communication function, internal institutionalization, resources, strategic communication.

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Fighting disinformation in the digital era: The Algerian government's approaches - Amar LOUCIF (Kasdi Merbah University of Ouargla, Algeria)

Disinformation is currently one of the most important topics in communication and political studies (Freelon & Wells, 2020). Recently, social media platforms are used widely to spread disinformation, which negatively affects trust in many democracies in the four corners of the world (Bennett & Livingston, 2018). Similarly, Abrusci (2024) considers online disinformation a real threat to the right of political participation, especially during elections. Since the emergence of Covid-19 in China, all countries in the world have seriously started to establish initiatives and approaches to combat online disinformation (Cipers et al., 2023). Algeria is one of the countries in Africa that has launched several approaches and initiatives to stop the spread of disinformation via social media platforms. The main objective of this research paper is to explore the effectiveness of the Algerian government's approach to combat online disinformation. To do this study, the researcher adopts a descriptive analytical method. In addition, data was gathered from various research sources (national and international literature), reports, documents, official journals, and websites to understand the different actions taken by the Algerian government to protect political participation from disinformation orders on social media platforms. Through this research work, we want to make an in-depth analysis of the impact of these actions in terms of limiting the spread of fake news on social networks.

Keywords: disinformation, trust, political communication, social media, fake news.

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M

Media narrative analysis for PR: An improved framework - Raluca MOISE (City University of London, United Kingdom)

Purpose

This paper explores the evolving role of media narratives in public relations (PR) and strategic communication, aiming to clarify core concepts and propose an enhanced analytical model. Despite a robust tradition of media narrative analysis in media studies, its application within PR remains underdeveloped and largely reactive, particularly confined to crisis contexts. The paper addresses these gaps by conducting a traditional literature review to redefine media narrative analysis in PR, incorporating power dynamics between organizations, media institutions, and publics.

Design/methodology/approach

A traditional literature review methodology is used to examine how media narrative and narrative analysis have been treated in PR and strategic communication literature. The paper analyses definitions, applications, and limitations of current narrative analysis approaches. The review highlights the rhetorical and structural elements of media narratives, and the absence of analytical tools to address power differentials between narrators (e.g., organizations, media) and audiences.

Findings

Initial findings indicate that media narrative is discussed primarily in crisis communication and lacks comprehensive analytical models in PR literature. Current narrative analysis tools omit critical aspects such as the narrator's voice and the audience's agency. The proposed model addresses this limitation by integrating three layers: structural components (plot, character, emplotment), rhetorical strategies (framing, metaphor, voice), and power dynamics (institutional power, audience stance). This improved framework offers a more holistic and socially grounded understanding of media narratives in PR.

Keywords: Media narrative, narrative analysis, public relations, analytical framework, power dynamics.

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Stylistic Trends in the Graphic Design of Contemporary Romanian Book Covers - Mihaela MOȚĂIANU (University of Bucharest, Romania)

În contextul globalizării industriilor culturale și al progresului tehnologic, studiul a urmărit să identifice tendințele vizuale folosind un set definit de categorii, cu accent pe modul în care tendințele internaționale de design grafic au fost integrate în industria editorială românească. În ciuda expansiunii cărților electronice și a cărților audio, cărțile tipărite au rămas o categorie importantă atât în librăriile tradiționale, cât și în cele online, ilustrând un peisaj de lectură diversificat, mai degrabă decât o trecere completă către digitalizare. Publicitatea direcționată, lansările de cărți virtuale și implicarea cititorilor prin intermediul rețelelor sociale au extins acoperirea cărților tipărite, demonstrând că digitalizarea nu înlocuiește tipărirea, ci mai degrabă remodelează modul în care cărțile sunt descoperite, comercializate și consumate (Penn 2018). Evoluția designului copertelor de carte este strâns legată de progresele tehnologiei digitale, astfel instrumente digitale precum suita de programe Adobe au revoluționat estetica copertelor de carte ducând la proliferarea anumitor stiluri de design. Progresele tehnologice, evoluția preferințelor cititorilor și inițiativele de sustenabilitate conduse de industrie vor remodela și mai mult procesele de producție, distribuție și consum de cărți, promovând noi modele de implicare și adaptare la piață (WIPO 2023). Analiza se bazează pe un corpus de cercetare ce cuprinde 116 coperte de ficțiune publicate în ianuarie 2025, selectate din patru librării online din România. Utilizând o grilă de codificare standardizată, copertele selectate au fost și evaluate sistematic pentru analiza stilurilor de design. Tendințele care au prezentat cele mai mari scoruri de frecvență au fost reținute pentru analize și discuții ulterioare. Rezultatele evidențiază adaptarea unor stiluri globale la specificul pieței românești, reflectând schimbările în preferințele vizuale ale consumatorilor și impactul noilor tehnologii în designul editorial.

Cuvinte cheie: tendințe în designul grafic; coperte de carte; ilustrație; caractere de literă; design de carte.

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Storytelling techniques employed on a traditional Romanian (Facebook) Meta page - Mădălina MORARU (University of Bucharest, Romania)

This research aims to examine the narrative strategies employed on social media to foster positive user attitudes or, at a minimum, to attract their attention. Social media users are attracted so much by stories, mostly life events, family dramas, and, sometimes simple slice of life shared daily. There is a strong connection between tabloid magazines and the type of content published daily on traditional Meta pages such as *Traditional românesc* and *Frumusețile României*. According to the Media Fact Book 2024, Facebook is accessed predominantly by Gen X (44.3%), followed by Millennials (31.7%), Gen Z (18.1%), and Baby Boomers (6%). This study focuses on the page *Frumusețile României (The Beauties of Romania)*, which presents itself as a news page and has approximately 1.3 million followers. Acerbi (2022) stated that negative emotions and curiosity are powerful narrative tools playing a central role in capturing and maintaining audience attention. These emotional triggers function as cognitive shortcuts, drawing readers into the story and encouraging continued engagement. In the context of digital media, particularly on platforms like Facebook, such emotional hooks are often strategically used to increase visibility, shares, and user interaction. Besides, Barrett (2019) considers that digital storytelling techniques are strongly influenced by diverse crisis.

The page (<https://www.facebook.com/www.Frumusetile.Romaniei.ro>) was monitored between April 17 and May 1, over a two-week period, as we observed that content is posted almost every hour or two. Posts were recorded daily at 6 p.m. Methodologically, the study relies primarily on framing analysis and discourse analysis. The approach is qualitative, aiming to identify thematic frames and the main narrative techniques used in a sample of 85 stories. One of the key findings of this research is that social and economic crises influence users' preferences for certain types of stories. A second major result is the identification of recurring thematic frames across most narratives, including: family secrets and conflicts, the motif of abandoned elderly people, savior figures, traditional cuisine, cultural celebrations, and mysterious deaths. Finally, the overarching narrative strategy employed on this Meta page echoes the structure and tone of legends or folk tales, drawing on familiar storytelling conventions to engage the audience emotionally and culturally. As a final observation, we noted a frequent use of AI-generated content on the page, which raises significant ethical concerns regarding the authenticity and credibility of the stories presented.

Keywords: digital story, Facebook, narrative techniques, authenticity, engagement.

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***TikTok's compliance with the Digital Services Act standards:
Protecting minors and tackling systemic risks - Adriana MUTU,
Luminița PĂTRAȘ (ESIC Business & Marketing School, Spain)***

Our paper investigates the recent developments in digital platform regulation reflecting the “European approach” to tackling very large online platforms potential to amplify online systemic risks that could harm and have negative or adverse effects on children (Drolsbach & Pröllochs, 2024; Leerssen, 2023; Mutu, 2023, 2024). It provides a groundbreaking original empirical assessment of TikTok’s compliance with the Digital Services Act (DSA) regarding the protection of minors from harmful content. This study employs a longitudinal empirical analysis based on public data from the DSA Transparency Database, focusing on TikTok’s Statements of Reasons (SoRs) related to content moderation actions under the “Protection of Minors” category between October 1, 2024, and January 1, 2025. The central unit of analysis is the SoR, which provides detailed information on content removal or restriction, allowing users to understand and challenge moderation decisions. The key variables analyzed include platform name, content type, category, decision ground, automated detection, and decision type. The data sets are ranging from 2.5 million to 3.8 million entries, with a total of 11.6 million entries. We conducted frequency, descriptive and cross-tabulation analysis of the main variable for the four time-points. Results reveal that registered complaints under the category of "protection of minors" constitute a significant portion of the overall dataset, highlighting the prevalence of harmful content on TikTok (Bartolo & Matamoros-Fernandez, 2023; Lacourt et al., 2024). The findings are examined in the context of TikTok’s policies for mitigating systemic risks that could encourage harmful behaviour and endanger minors. This study contributes to the scientific understanding of regulatory compliance under the new European digital legislation, which seeks to address systemic risks that may threaten children's fundamental rights.

Keywords: Digital Services Act, DSA Transparency Database, TikTok, systemic risks, minors.

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P

The Arm's Length Principle in the Media Field in Norway versus Romania and the European Media Freedom Act - Raluca PETRE, Adrian ANTON (Ovidius University of Constanța, Romania)

The principle of the arm's length is a public policy instrument, that has at its core the fundamental idea of separation of powers. It has started to be used in the field of cultural production in the second part of the twentieth century. The arm's length principle refers to the delegation of the executive function in terms of decision making, as well as contracting, to an independent cultural/media body.

In this contribution, we analyse the way the arm's length principle is applied in Norway in contrast with Romania. The object of analysis is the public financing of the press in the two countries. On the one hand there is Norway, a country with a long tradition of democracy and practices of separation of powers, where the principle of the arm's length is applied since the late sixties to finance the press. It represents the model against which Romania is contrasted. On the other hand, Romania is a fairly young democracy with a long legacy of lack of separation of powers, and solid roots of politics over the media. We observe how the subfield of cultural magazines is an area where the principle of the arm's length has been institutionalised at the level of the Romanian Ministry of Culture, while the mainstream media outlets represent an area where power does not really let go. This phenomenon occurs by means of political parties using public money for communication services with commercial contracts that escape public scrutiny.

In this context, we problematise the novelties that the European Media Freedom Act brings to the media landscape, especially the requirements regarding the transparency of media. We observe how this regulation can be a good opportunity for genuinely expanding the arm's length principle to other Romanian media outlets.

Keywords: arm's length, public policy, press financing, Romania, Norway

Russian strategic narratives in the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine and Romania: the case of the soft power agency

Rossotrudnichestvo - Marianna PRYSIAZHNIUK (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Abstract

The Federal Agency for the Commonwealth of Independent States, Compatriots Living Abroad, and International Humanitarian Cooperation—commonly known as Rossotrudnichestvo — operates abroad through a network of so-called Russian Houses (with variations in naming depending on the host country). Rossotrudnichestvo mainly serves as the Russian state's core soft power institution, playing a central role in instrumentalizing history through primarily cultural, educational, and media-oriented activities, which are designed to engage diverse social groups within host countries and often disrupting local socio-political contexts and broader regional stability imposing strategic narratives of the Russian foreign politics into agenda of the host countries.

Purpose

This article examines how the Russian soft power agency promotes strategic narratives aligned with the Kremlin's geopolitical objectives to shape the perception of host countries' political and geopolitical events. The article focuses on Ukraine, Moldova, and Romania, mapping Rossotrudnichestvo activities and analyzing the correlation between promoted strategic narratives and significant political and geopolitical events.

Methodology

The article includes (1) a theoretical framework for understanding strategic narratives and their role in Russia's foreign policy and political discourse; (2) a comprehensive institutional profile of Rossotrudnichestvo; (3) a contextualized mapping of activities across the three target countries with their aligning to the strategic narratives of the Russian foreign politics; and (4) a correlation analysis between those narratives and activities and significant geopolitical and political developments in the region. The findings demonstrate that the strategic narratives disseminated through Rossotrudnichestvo operate less as mechanisms of attraction — typical of conventional soft power — and more as foreign interference and coercion instruments.

Keywords: strategic narratives, soft power, FIMI, Rossotrudnichestvo

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R

Fear Instrumentalized: Analyzing the Realities of Political Discourse during Romanian Elections - Paula RAȚIU (Babeș-Bolyai University, Romania)

Purpose

Highly affected by and contributing to advances in technology and societal changes, communication continually reveals and constructs realities. Nowadays, these processes take place especially through (political) discourse and within the spaces created by social media platforms. The purpose of this paper relies on some current realities and on the studies dedicated to them. A reality is that social media influences the themes and discursive styles of politicians and they use technology to frame issues and exploit emotions in order to manipulate as many people as possible. Given that emotions such as fear have been efficiently increasing the success of radical, populist or isolationist views, analyzing their usage can be useful for both the public and researchers. Therefore, this paper is meant to explore the relationship between social media, political discourse and emotional appeals, while focusing on how these elements communicate with each other.

Design/methodology/approach

The theoretical coverage done in the paper generated a main research question, which is “How was fear used and how is fear being used today in the construction of social media political discourse?” In order to find answers to this question, the method used is a qualitative discourse analysis, concentrated on content posted by candidates involved in the Romanian presidential elections from 2020 and 2025. A comparative study has the potential to emphasize patterns and changes in the mechanisms of Romanian politics and society, revealing what and how possible presidents communicate with the citizens.

(Potential) Findings

Even though the current paper could benefit from future research focusing on other discursive elements or on the public’s response to campaign discourses, it contributes to communication studies by exploring how people are encouraged to fear differences, how emotions become efficient vessels for ideologies or how platforms can dictate the relationship dynamics between people and their most important representatives.

Keywords: political communication, social media, discourse analysis, fear appeals, election campaigns

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S

Is it a Scam?: Social media scams in South Africa as part of a Disinformation Ecosystem - Alette SCHOON (Rhodes University, South Africa)

Purpose

This paper uses several South African case studies to argue for the importance of studying scams to better understand disinformation on social media in the Global Majority World. Current scholarship on disinformation in these countries focus on the need to consider disinformation contextually (Wasserman & Madrid-Morales, 2022) and to go beyond normative approaches and to also consider disinformation as an everyday activity within a powerful global industry (Ong & Cabañes, 2018). Nevertheless, scholars appear to restrict their analysis of disinformation to explicitly political messages addressed at a general public (See Roberts & Karekwaivanane, 2024), neglecting the everyday more private experience of the ‘scam’.

In Global Majority countries such as the Democratic Republic of Congo, Pype and Makaya (2022) have described the ubiquity of falsehoods and scams as deeply embedded in the society, creating “cultures of deception”. In societies in the Global Majority World are characterised by informality (Simone, 2004), ordinary people are frequently at the mercy of scammers, and constantly need to assess whether something is real or fake, a genuine interaction or a scam. Making sense of everyday events and media as potentially deceptive, is therefore an everyday skill and communal pastime, which manifests in ordinary conversations and increasingly in online “Scam Alert” groups.

Design/methodology/approach

This paper examines online commercial scams in the South African context, focusing on a qualitative analysis of three case studies: an online walkthrough of a scam website selling bitcoin to South Africans, a thematic analysis of South African Scam Alert Facebook groups warning users of current scams and of a multimodal thematic analysis of a set of TikTok videos discussing a young South African influencer “Dr Matthew” who sold remedies online posing as a medical doctor”.

Findings

I show how these scams potentially have much broader social impact, affecting overall trust in social institutions. Since scammers use the language of verification employed by journalists, it further undermines the authority of the profession. I therefore argue that to address overtly political disinformation, which has to date been the major concern of Disinformation

Studies, we need to start recognising the integrated reality of this world of commercial scams as part of what I call a broader disinformation ecosystem.

Keywords: Disinformation, Scams, Global Majority World, Social Media, South Africa.

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Non-transparency of online media ownership in Bosnia and Herzegovina: A dual threat to journalism and citizens - Lamija SILAJDŽIĆ (University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)

Abstract

Non-transparency of the ownership of online media in Bosnia and Herzegovina poses threat to both media professionals and citizens. Anonymous and unregulated online media has contributed to the spread of malicious content and disinformation (Cvjetićanin et al., 2019) and the marginalization of credible media (Silajdžić, 2025). By prioritizing virality, profit or political influence over credibility and professionalism, such media environments often overshadow quality (professional) journalism, undermining the role of the media in democratic society. On the other hand, lack of media and information literacy among citizens (Vajzović et al. 2021, Hodžić and Sokol 2019, Silajdžić 2023) make it difficult for audiences to understand the difference between legitimate media sources and non-transparent deceptive ones. The paper used qualitative analysis of relevant research papers and legal framework, and semi-structured interviews with media professionals (N=6), to highlight the urgent need for media ownership transparency (Osmančević and Šušnjar, 2021) and media and information literacy education. Two key research questions are: How do unregulated anonymous online media affect credible media? How do they affect citizens? The results indicate that without transparent media ownership and media-information literate citizens, there is no preservation of the credibility of journalism, nor quality information for citizens. Consequently, no functional democracy either.

Keywords: media ownership, non-transparency, media professionals, citizens, Bosnia and Herzegovina

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Adoption of digital marketing strategies on small local businesses: Case study: Lumea Espresso, Oravița (Caraș-Severin) - Codruța-Diana SIMIONESCU, Daniel-Darius ONEȚIU (West University of Timișoara, Romania)

Purpose

The evolution from traditional to digital marketing marks a fundamental shift in how businesses engage with consumers (Kotler, 2016). Digital marketing places the individual at the core of the marketing strategy, emphasizing empathy, personalization, and meaningful engagement. Meanwhile, the changing in consumer expectations, and the growing importance of authenticity and trust, asks business owners to foster deeper connections with their customers, by listening to their needs, co-creating value, and building long-term relationships (Kotler, 2021). In an increasingly dynamic marketplace adoption of the adequate web based marketing tools, especially for SME is challenging (Coman, Popica, Rezeanu, 2020). The purpose of the present paper is to make a qualitative analysis on how the adoption of an integrated social-media advertising strategy, the shift from traditional marketing to a human-centric one and inclusion of an online shop for a local small business brings increased benefits for the brand and the turnover.

Design/methodology/approach

A qualitative literature review method was used, along with a qualitative approach, such as semi-structured interview, ethnographic research and the analysis of data obtained from social media platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Tik Tok).

(Potential) Findings

The findings indicate that while digital marketing offers significant benefits (increased customer reach, cost-effectiveness, improved customer engagement, access to an international market), many small businesses struggle with limited resources, digital literacy, and strategic planning. The recommended practical steps for local businesses are: to enhance their digital presence, invest in acquiring digital skills or/and employ social media specialists and change the entrepreneurial mind set. This research contributes to understanding how small enterprises can leverage digital strategies to remain competitive in an increasingly online marketplace.

Keywords: human-centric marketing, small local business, integrated social media, mind set, authenticity and trust

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Stylistic trends and aesthetic strategies of Romanian advertisements published on digital platforms - Corina SÎRB, Iasmina PETROVICI (West University of Timișoara, Romania)

Purpose

The aim of this study is to reveal that, in the current context of the influx of advertisements distributed on digital platforms, the aesthetic function of advertising design is just as important as its marketing and persuasive functions. In advertising design practice, stylistic trends are periodically employed to meet both the visual identity requirements of brands and the needs and preferences of audiences (Inglis, 2023; Landa, 2021; Alstiel & Grow, 2012). Along with other visual and compositional elements, style individualizes online advertisements, giving them a distinctive appearance and contributing to brand visual identity.

Methodology

The study proposes a semiotic analysis of the visual content from a sample of Romanian advertisements distributed on digital platforms during the 2024–2025 period. The semiotic approach will reveal how design elements create meaning and support both the aesthetic and persuasive functions of advertising materials. The selection of visual materials will be based on a diversity of digital platforms, including both display advertisements and sponsored content from social media networks. Advertisements selected for analysis will be those with high visibility, either through high engagement rates (likes, comments, shares) or through frequent appearances in campaigns by local and national brands. The selection criteria will also consider stylistic diversity and relevance to the target audience.

In addition to the semiotic analysis, the study will integrate theoretical perspectives on user behavior in the digital environment, such as the *Limited attention theory* (Simon, 1971), *Dual processing theory* (Kahneman, 2011) and *Uses and gratifications theory* (Blumler & Katz, 1974, Ruggiero, 2000). These perspectives will allow for a contextualized interpretation of visual consumption preferences and will help explain the prevalence of certain graphic design styles in relation to the dynamics of online interactions.

(Potential) Findings

In digital design, style determines the aesthetic expressiveness of advertising materials. It is the element that gives distinctiveness to Romanian advertisements distributed on digital platforms, enhancing brand identity and visual recognition and ensuring information retention. Through this mixed approach, we believe that the research will provide a deeper understanding of how visual style in digital advertising simultaneously meets both the aesthetic and pragmatic demands of brand communication.

Keywords: advertising design, Romanian online advertisements, graphic design style, aesthetic expression

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Spatial Inequalities in Media Coverage and Environmental Communication: A Case Study of Tulcea County and the Danube Delta in Romania - Romina SURUGIU, Aurelian GIUGĂL (University of Bucharest, Romania), Alexandru GAVRIȘ (Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania)

Abstract

This research applies the concept of “news deserts” (Abernathy, 2023; Gulyas et al., 2023) to examine spatial inequalities in media coverage and their implications for environmental communication in Romania, with a particular focus on Tulcea County. The study highlights a deepening “spatial divide” between media-rich regions, such as Bucharest, home to over 20,000 media professionals, and media-poor areas, where fewer than 100 individuals work in the sector. Drawing on official statistical data, we demonstrate how this disparity exacerbates inequalities in access to information, particularly in economically marginalised regions like Tulcea, where local media face editorial pressures, limited audiences, and political influences. The paper further explores the role of media in shaping public discourse on environmental policies through a case study of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Applying topic modeling to a corpus of 3,069 articles from national and local outlets, we analyze media framing and stakeholder representation in coverage of this protected area. Preliminary findings reveal that both local and national media amplify institutional voices while marginalizing community perspectives, reinforcing a top-down narrative that may hinder the alignment of conservation goals with socio-economic equity. In Tulcea, a region directly impacted by environmental regulations yet underserved by local journalism, this media bias exacerbates existing information gaps.

By bridging the “news desert” framework with environmental communication research, this study underscores the need for more inclusive media representation and participatory approaches in reporting, particularly in regions where media scarcity intersects with critical ecological and socio-economic challenges.

Keywords: News deserts & media inequality; environmental communication; spatial divide; Romania; Tulcea County; Danube Delta; topic modeling; media representation.

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An Examination of Mental Health in Romanian Journalism: Preliminary Data and Interpretations - Emilia ȘERCAN (University of Bucharest, Romania), Bogdan VOICU (“Lucian Blaga” University, Romania)

The journalistic profession is recognized among occupations with high levels of stress, and awareness of this issue has generated significant global concern regarding the mental health of its practitioners.

This paper presents the preliminary findings of a survey conducted in the spring of 2025, which aimed to assess perceptions of mental health among journalists in Romania. The study, based on an online self-administered questionnaire completed by 345 journalists, analyzes factors contributing to stress and job satisfaction, the prevalence of burnout, experiences related to workplace abuse, and access to psychological support.

The results indicate concerning levels of perceived stress, with the main factors identified by journalists being: (1) heavy and unpredictable workload (61% high/very high stress); (2) income (61% high/very high stress); (3) work-life imbalance (56% high/very high stress); and (4) the relationship with state institutions (52% high/very high stress).

Although the majority of respondents (89%) believe that psychological support procedures offered by newsrooms are necessary, such provisions are largely absent (80%), while the topic of mental health is seldom discussed within the profession.

Furthermore, journalists perceive low levels of respect and trust from society, a finding corroborated by [existing data](#) showing public trust in the media at a historic low of 8%. The findings underscore the importance of understanding mental health issues, as well as the factors that generate or exacerbate the high level of occupational stress among journalists.

Keywords: mental health, journalists, Romania, burnout, working conditions

Digital Populism, TikTok, and the Algorithmic Erosion of Democracy: Big Data Insights from Romania's 2024 Elections - Adriana ȘTEFĂNEL, Iulian VEGHEȘ, Roland ÎMPUȘCATU (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper investigates how TikTok, as an emotionally driven and algorithmically curated platform, facilitated the rise of populist candidate Călin Georgescu during Romania's 2024 presidential elections. By examining the communicative affordances of TikTok in relation to populist strategy, the study explores the broader implications of platform logic for democratic erosion and political polarization.

Design/methodology/approach

The study employs a *big data* approach to analyze the digital footprint of Georgescu's campaign on TikTok. Using a custom data pipeline that scrapes and processes thousands of public TikTok videos, comments, hashtags, and engagement metrics (likes, shares, watch time), the research integrates:

- Hashtag frequency and co-occurrence analysis, to trace dominant narrative frames (e.g., “#romaniaverde”, “#antiglobalism”, “#tradition”);
- Sentiment analysis and emotion classification, to measure affective intensity and tone of user comments;
- Network analysis, to map the structure of engagement communities and identify key amplification nodes (influencers, algorithm-favored content);
- Temporal diffusion modeling, to study how specific messages went viral and how engagement evolved across the campaign period.

(Potential) Findings

The analysis reveals that Georgescu's campaign did not rely on coordinated bots or sponsored ads, but rather on organic virality driven by algorithmically favored civilizational narratives. Populist and anti-system hashtags were semantically clustered around themes of purity, national rebirth, and elite betrayal. High emotional engagement (especially moral anger and nostalgic pride) predicted virality, and content dissemination followed a hub-and-spoke model, centered on a few influential TikTok creators. The absence of narrative counter-strategies from mainstream parties allowed disinformation and populist tropes to dominate the platform.

Keywords: TikTok, big data, sentiment analysis, populist narratives, Romanian elections

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Emotional agenda-setting and disinformation in social media -

Manuela ȚIMBOLSCHI-PREOTEASA (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper investigates the mechanisms behind social media disinformation during the annulled Romanian presidential elections, focusing on how social media platforms reshape the public agenda.

Theoretical framework

Grounded in agenda-setting theory (McCombs & Shaw, 1972) and Habermas's concept of the public sphere (1991), the study explores how social media transforms the nature of agenda-setting from an information-oriented model, typical of traditional media, to an emotionally driven, attention-based model. Shaw and Valenzuela (2007) identified the “pervasiveness of mass media” as a major source of journalism’s influence on audiences. Mapping the mechanisms of agenda-setting in the social media environment involves identifying how the agenda diverges, the emotional triggers embedded in themes and narratives, and how content is produced - whether it is artificially generated - and whether audience reactions and forms of engagement are genuine or fabricated (e.g., through *trolling*, *astroturfing*, and other manipulative techniques). The definition of disinformation and related concepts will draw on the frameworks developed by Wardle (2021) and Wardle & Derakhshan (2017), while also incorporating related concepts such as “echo chambers” (Arguedas *et al.*, 2022), “filter bubbles” (Pariser, 2011), and other relevant theories applicable to social media. Special attention will be given to the role of AI in amplifying disinformation - through algorithmic curation, automated content generation, and the use of bots or deepfakes - which intensifies the spread, emotional impact, and perceived legitimacy of misleading narratives.

Design/methodology/approach

The research employs content analysis on a corpus of approximately 100 social media posts from TikTok and Facebook from the period November 2024 to April 2025. The analysis aims to identify patterns of disinformation, conspiracy narratives, and emotionally charged content used to divert public attention.

Findings (anticipated)

The study expects to find that social media increasingly replaces fact-based agenda-setting with emotionally manipulative and sensational content. Disinformation is frequently paired with non-reporting and attention-capturing themes designed to engage psychological

vulnerabilities, aligning with the dynamics of an attention economy. These tactics create an alternative agenda divergent to verified information, a trend also reflected in mainstream media, which has exhibited increasing "polarisation and inconsistencies" (Toma et al., 2024), as documented in the Media Pluralism Monitor research (2024).

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U

The digital self between authenticity and performance: An exploration of online practices among young women in Romania - Georgiana UDREA, Roxana BUZILĂ (SNSPA, Romania)

Scop

Într-o lume în care universul rețelelor sociale online constituie un mediu fundamental de existență, construirea și negocierea sinelui pe platformele digitale reprezintă nu doar o practică identitară relevantă, ci și un subiect de cercetare deosebit de actual și pertinent. În acest context, lucrarea de față investighează modul în care tinerele din România își conturează identitatea digitală pe platforme precum Instagram, TikTok și Facebook, analizând strategiile de autoprezentare utilizate, raportarea la presiunea comparației sociale, dar și influența proceselor de (auto)obiectificare și comodificare asupra formării sinelui în mediul digital.

Metodologie/abordare

Printr-o abordare calitativă, bazată pe interviuri în profunzime semi-structurate cu respondente din mediul urban, cercetarea explorează discrepanța și tensiunile dintre sinele autentic/real, sinele proiectat și cel validat social. Întrebările de cercetare care au ghidat demersul empiric sunt: *Cum utilizează tinerele rețelele sociale online?*; *Care sunt strategiile utilizate de tinere în construirea identității din mediul online?*; *În ce măsură tendințele spre idealizarea sinelui online conduc către (auto)obiectificare și/sau comodificare?*.

Rezultate preconizate/obținute

Chiar dacă participantele afirmă că nu se lasă influențate de numărul de urmăritori, de feedbackul negativ sau de tendințele promovate în social media, strategiile adoptate în crearea profilului digital evidențiază rolul central pe care mediul online îl joacă în modelarea sinelui. Astfel, rețelele sociale se conturează ca spații esențiale nu doar de exprimare, ci și de validare simbolică și negociere continuă a identității personale.

Aceste constatări au implicații importante pentru înțelegerea proceselor de construire a identității în mediul digital, subliniind necesitatea dezvoltării unor strategii de alfabetizare media care să contribuie la formarea unui sine digital autentic, echilibrat și rezilient în fața presiunilor normative exercitate de mediul online.

Cuvinte-cheie: rețele sociale online, sine digital, (auto)obiectificare, comodificare, interviuri în profunzime, studente române

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V

Digital propaganda and the polarization of political beliefs: How social media distorts democratic debate - Mihai VACARIU (University of Bucharest, Romania)

Purpose

This paper examines the impact of digital propaganda and algorithm-driven content amplification on political belief formation and democratic discourse. It explores how social media platforms, particularly TikTok and Facebook, shape political arguments, influence voter perception, and contribute to ideological polarization. By analyzing recent case studies from Romanian elections, the paper investigates the mechanisms through which disinformation, selective exposure, and cognitive biases influence the processing of political arguments and voter decision-making.

Design/methodology/approach

The study employs a qualitative and data-driven approach, combining content analysis of viral political narratives on social media with insights from political psychology and communication studies. It integrates findings from recent reports on digital manipulation in elections, as well as theoretical frameworks on motivated reasoning and information cascades. The paper also references experimental studies on conformity bias and echo chambers to explain why false beliefs persist despite corrective information.

(Potential) Findings

The research highlights several critical insights:

1. Algorithmic amplification – Political content, particularly disinformation, benefits from the design of social media algorithms, which prioritize engagement over factual accuracy.
2. Cognitive and social biases – Individuals are prone to motivated reasoning, reinforcing pre-existing political beliefs instead of engaging with balanced arguments.
3. Weaponization of influencers – Political actors exploit non-political influencers to bypass restrictions on political advertising, making propaganda less detectable and more persuasive.
4. Selective exposure and polarization – Rather than fostering deliberation, social media exacerbates ideological divides by reinforcing users' existing perspectives.
5. Case study: The Romanian 2024 elections – The viral rise of Călin Georgescu illustrates how artificial visibility on TikTok can shape public perception and election outcomes, even in the absence of a formal political campaign.

The findings suggest that current strategies for combating disinformation (e.g., fact-checking, content moderation) are insufficient, as they fail to address the structural incentives that drive the spread of political misinformation. The study argues for greater transparency in algorithmic content distribution and regulatory frameworks to counteract digital propaganda's impact on democratic processes.

Keywords: Political communication, digital propaganda, social media algorithms, cognitive bias, disinformation.

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Rethinking trust in the post-digital age: How generative AI deepfakes reality - Amina VATREŠ (University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)

Purpose

This paper investigates the communicative implications of deepfake technologies within the broader context of generative AI-driven disinformation. Moving beyond the immediate material impacts, it explores how hyper-realistic synthetic media artifacts – especially deepfakes – reshape the communicative space by blurring distinctions between reality and fabrication. In doing so, it focuses on the epistemological fragmentation emerging in digital media environments, where algorithmically mediated content not only circulates disinformation but also destabilizes the very conditions necessary for shared public discourse and collective meaning-making. By examining deepfakes as both a product and a catalyst of a transformed communication ecosystem, this study situates them within broader trends of filter bubbles, filter clashes, and the erosion of epistemic trust.

Design/methodology/approach

The study adopts a conceptual and case-study-driven approach, integrating media philosophy and the theory of algorithmic mediatization. It first maps deepfakes as communicative artifacts deeply embedded in algorithmically curated digital ecosystems that intensify disinformation dynamics. Then, it analyzes two emblematic cases: (1) the deepfake video of Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky, which exemplifies the use of synthetic media to manipulate public perception during crisis communication, and (2) the controversy surrounding the alleged deepfake of Gabonese President Ali Bongo, which highlights how even mere suspicion of deepfake involvement can destabilize political trust and trigger unrest. These cases are used to demonstrate how deepfakes not only actively deceive but also fuel a communicative climate of radical uncertainty.

Findings

As a manifestation of generative AI technologies, deepfakes intensify two interlinked risks: first, they serve as powerful tools for the dissemination of disinformation exploiting emotional and cognitive vulnerabilities, and second, they are fostering epistemological fragmentation, where the authenticity of any digital content can be called into question. As deepfakes become more sophisticated and socially pervasive, they not only fabricate false narratives but also create a communicative environment where real and authentic events can be easily dismissed – “liar’s dividend” (Chesney & Citron 2019). Moreover, acting as both symptoms and accelerators of an emerging communicative paradigm in which the boundaries between reality and fiction are not only blurred but strategically contested, this paper sees deepfakes both a product and a catalyst of a transformed communication ecosystem,

situating them within the broader trends of filter bubbles, filter clashes, and the erosion of epistemic trust.

Keywords: generative AI; deepfakes; erosion of trust; epistemic fragmentation

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